

The Roots of Disparity: Exploring Socioeconomic Influences on Early Childhood Development

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Introduction

Approximately 10% of the Israeli population is under the age of four, in contrast to an average of 5.4% in the OECD (OECD, 2020). This demographic composition generates unusually high demand in Israel for educational and health services for young children and families. Israel's health system provides universal, accessible health services, including Tipat Halav (Hebrew for *drop of milk*) clinics that provide cost-free, universal pediatric preventive care to children from birth to age six. These clinics are at the forefront of safeguarding the health of Israel's young population and provide many services including routine vaccinations and surveillance of child growth and development, which is conducted by assessing age-appropriate milestones from four domains: gross motor skills, fine motor skills, language development, and personal-social development. These milestones have been adapted from well-established developmental scales (Ball, 1977; Frankenburg et al., 1992; Frankenburg & Dodds, 1967; Provence et al., 1995). Recently, an evidence-based surveillance scale was created based on the Tipat Halav dataset (Sudry et al., 2022).

Future Taub Center research will delve into the Tipat Halav database and examine socioeconomic differences in milestone attainment. In preparation for these studies, the current paper reviews the scholarly literature on early childhood development, focusing in particular on its relationship with family SES (socioeconomic status) within each developmental domain assessed in the Tipat Halav clinics. The key goal is to understand the degree and timing of unfolding disparities, and shed light on environmental influences on developmental paths in each domain.

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Background

Early childhood is the most formative stage in human development (Bailey, 2001; Blossfeld et al., 2017; Phillips & Shonkoff, 2000). It is a critical period characterized by rapid growth and skill acquisition that sets the trajectory for children's future well-being and functioning (Gilmore et al., 2018; Lejarraga, 2012). Child development can be assessed by (Bilu et al., 2023) tests that measure a child's ability in a given skill at a certain age and screening tests that ascertain if a child is at risk for developmental delays (DD)¹ (Fernald et al., 2009). Screening for early childhood development is conducted around the world by measuring *milestone attainment*. Milestones are categorized into groups by domain. They include language, gross motor, fine motor, and personal-social skills. Developmental screens consist of a list of domain-specific milestones that children are expected to achieve by certain ages. If a child does not reach a developmental milestone on time, it may indicate DD, which could imply the need for additional monitoring and possibly interventions.

Development does not occur in a vacuum: children learn and grow in interaction with their environments (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 1998; Nelson et al., 2019). Nature and nurture work together in tandem: children's genetic predispositions interact with their environments creating complex developmental trajectories. Early life experiences and environments heavily influence early childhood development and life course outcomes. The quality of a young child's environment is of utmost importance for healthy development (Phillips & Shonkoff, 2000). Yet children are not born into, nor raised in, equal environments. Family circumstance, measured by income or SES, heavily influences children's developmental potential (Bradley & Corwyn, 2002; Fernald et al., 2009, 2012). Family SES comprises many components including parental education, occupation, and household assets. While family income is a significant factor that relates to SES, they do not completely overlap. For instance, a family with a high income may still have a lower SES if parental education or occupational prestige are not equally elevated.

1 For example, an ability test for early language skills would provide a continuous score for vocabulary, whereas a screening test would examine if the child begins to produce words by a certain age.

In addition to biological, anthropometric measures (e.g., weight for age, premature birth, low birth weight, health complications), low family SES and maternal education are significant risk factors for early childhood DDs (Acharya et al., 2023; Ahmadi Doulabi et al., 2017; Potijk et al., 2013). Young children from disadvantaged homes are more likely to experience DD because they are disproportionately exposed to risk factors such as poor nutrition, chronic stress, overcrowded housing, exposure to violence, lack of stimulating toys and language, and environmental toxins that negatively impact development (Bradley & Corwyn, 2002; Duncan et al., 2017; Fernald et al., 2009; Walker et al., 2011). Brain imaging studies have found that brain regions associated with language, memory, executive function, and emotion processing are particularly vulnerable to the effects of poverty, and these differences are apparent as early as the first year of life (Farah, 2017; Johnson et al., 2016; Noble et al., 2012, 2015; Noble & Farah, 2013; Noble & Giebler, 2020).

The effect of family income, specifically during early childhood, has a greater impact on academic outcomes than during other periods in childhood (Shay & Shavit, 2022). Even considering upward mobility from economic disadvantage in early childhood to subsequent improved financial circumstances, the experience of poverty from the prenatal period through the earliest years negatively predicts cognition at age seven and reading skills in kindergarten (Johnson et al., 2022; Riser et al., 2022). These findings demonstrate how family circumstance in early childhood plays a pivotal role in the unfolding development of core competencies during this time, which shape brain development and lay the foundation for emerging skills for the whole life course.

Zooming out, the prevalence of DD is higher in areas with higher poverty rates, such as rural regions (Acharya et al., 2023; Ahishakiye et al., 2019; Bello et al., 2013; Bishwokarma et al., 2022; Rubio-Codina et al., 2015; Sharma et al., 2019; Wei et al., 2015). On the global scale, children from low- and middle-income countries are at greater risk for DD than children from wealthier countries (Emerson et al., 2018; Fink et al., 2020; Gil et al., 2020). In 2010, an estimated 250 million children worldwide were at risk for DD due to exposure to stunting and extreme poverty (Lu et al., 2016). Altogether, these findings demonstrate that poverty, both on the family and national levels, puts children at risk of not fulfilling their developmental potential (Fernald et al., 2012; Fink et al., 2020).

Early language development

Language is a complex, multifaceted system that utilizes a convention of sounds for the purpose of communication (Hoff, 2014). Newborn infants, who initially cannot speak or understand language, gradually develop the ability to comprehend, speak, question, and express themselves. By around six months, most babies recognize their own name, and by eight to ten months, they understand a few more words. Typically, children say their first word around their first birthday. During the second year of life, children's vocabulary rapidly grows from a handful to hundreds of words, a pattern observed across different languages (Frank et al., 2021). Early language skills are mainly divided into receptive and expressive communication (Hoff, 2014). Receptive communication measures assess language comprehension (e.g., understands simple instructions), while expressive communication measures assess word production (e.g., says 2–3 words).

Why early language matters

Early language skills are consistently one of the strongest predictors of school readiness,² reading skills, and academic achievement (Alloway & Alloway, 2010; Burchinal et al., 2016; Grøver, 2017; Hoff, 2013; Lee & Burkam, 2002; Scarborough, 2009). Many standardized academic and IQ tests rely heavily on language skills, and vocabulary at school entry predicts later achievement. These seeds are planted early: individual differences in vocabulary at ages three to four persist through childhood, such that children with a rich vocabulary in early childhood continue to have a rich vocabulary later (Bornstein et al., 2014; Hoff, 2014; Rowe et al., 2012).

Adding family SES to the mix complicates matters since it positively associates with language skills, school readiness, and academic achievement (Brooks-Gunn & Duncan, 1997; Farah et al., 2006; Marks et al., 2006; Merz et al., 2020; Noble et al., 2006; Pace et al., 2017; Sirin, 2005). Yet, most research examines these relationships in pairs, which yields an incomplete picture. One study longitudinally examined the relationship between family SES, early language skills, and school readiness by tracking how individual differences in family SES and the pace of vocabulary growth amongst toddlers aged 14–46 months

2 School readiness refers to a set of behaviors and skills required for successful schooling including cognitive, social, emotional, and motor skills (see Duncan et al., 2007).

predicted school readiness at 54 months (Rowe et al., 2012). It found that SES, measured by parental education and family income, was a significant predictor of vocabulary growth during toddlerhood, and this growth predicted vocabulary skills at school entry. Similarly, other studies have found that SES-based differences in language ability at the onset of schooling predict later academic achievement (Durham et al., 2007; Lee & Burkam, 2002; Walker et al., 1994). These findings suggest that differences in language abilities among children from low- and high-SES families have significant implications for school success, with the SES achievement gap discernible before children even set foot in a school (Hoff, 2013).

An additional concern in early childhood language development is the early identification of developmental and learning disorders, which disproportionately affect children by family SES. Children from low SES homes are at a greater risk of developing language and communication-related disorders, including autism spectrum disorder and developmental dyslexia (Durkin et al., 2010; Nowell et al., 2015; Peterson & Pennington, 2015; Ribeiro et al., 2023; Scarborough, 2009; Thomas et al., 2012). Despite the higher risk factor for language disorders, prevalence rates for diagnoses of autism and dyslexia can be skewed, with higher rates observed among children from wealthier homes (Rai et al., 2012; Schelbe et al., 2022). This discrepancy may stem from lower access to diagnostic and other related services for children from disadvantaged homes, which could be due to limited financial and time resources in low SES homes or lower awareness of available services in their communities. Early diagnosis is crucial for successful interventions for these disorders, placing children from low SES homes at an even greater disadvantage if they are not diagnosed early. An in-depth understanding of early childhood language developmental trajectories among children from all SES levels can help identify these disorders across diverse populations and provide all children with the support they need irrespective of family background.

SES disparities in early childhood language development

Research has consistently found that children from disadvantaged homes have poorer language skills than their peers, and the language gap contributes to later differences in reading and school success (Abufhele et al., 2022; Farah et al., 2006; Hoff, 2013; Merz et al., 2020; Noble et al., 2006). But when does the language gap between children from low- and high-SES homes begin to

appear? Findings from multiple studies have that found SES disparities in language skills are detectable as early as the second year of life, and the gap widens from these early years, suggesting that the groups have differential development trajectories for language (Arriaga et al., 1998; Betancourt et al., 2015; Dailey & Bergelson, 2022; Fernald et al., 2013; Halle et al., 2009; Hoff, 2003; Huttenlocher et al., 2010, 2010; Noble et al., 2015; Rowe et al., 2012, 2012; Rowe & Goldin-Meadow, 2009). Betancourt et al. (2015) found SES-based differences in seven-month-old infants' preverbal skills. However, the generalizability of this finding is low due to the small sample size and the fact that the participants were exclusively female.

Arriaga et al. (1998) compared the language skills of toddlers (16–30 months old) from very low-income homes (younger siblings of Head Start participants) to toddlers from middle-income homes on a standardized communication scale (MacArthur Communicative Development Inventory). They found that the children from very-low income homes scored significantly lower on all the scale indices: size of expressive vocabulary, age of appearance of word combinations, and utterance complexity. Their findings highlight the language gap between toddlers from high- and low-income homes and the importance of diversity when building norms for assessment tools.

One study analyzed data from the Early Childhood Longitudinal Study Birth Cohort (ECLS-B)³ and examined language and cognitive differences among nine and 24-month-old infants by family income level (Halle et al., 2009). Findings from 9-month-olds suggest subtle differences in the assessment measures between infants from high- and low-income homes (explores objects, explores purposefully, jabbars expressively, early problem-solving, and names objects). At 24 months, the gap was more apparent, and there were significant differences in all measures (receptive vocabulary, expressive vocabulary, listening/comprehension, matching/discrimination, early counting). The study also examined the cumulative effect of additional risk factors associated with low-income homes, e.g., low maternal education, minority status, and non-English speaking home, and compared children from low-income homes to

3 The ECLS-B is a nationally representative sample of over 10,000 children born in the U.S. in 2001, conducted by the National Center for Education Statistics in the U.S. Department of Education. Data were collected at three time points (9 months, 2 years old, and 4 years old) to inform policy makers, researchers, parents, teachers, and early childhood care providers of information on early childhood development, health, and education (see Andreassen & Fletcher, 2007).

children with additional risk factors. The effect of cumulative risk factors was small for 9-month-olds, while at 24 months, two or three additional risk factors created very large disparities. The findings suggest that language disparities emerge very early and are clearly evident by age two, and cumulative risk can contribute more to the gaps.

Fernald et al. (2013) compared children aged 18 and 24 months old from low and high SES homes based on the Hollingshead Four Factor Index of Socioeconomic Status⁴ in two language tasks: vocabulary (based on a parent report of expressive vocabulary) and a looking-while-listening task. In the looking-while-listening task, babies are shown two pictures of familiar objects and simultaneously hear labels for one of the pictures; looking time and accuracy were measured to assess language receptivity. SES disparities were evident in both language tasks among the 18-month-olds. For the 24-month-olds, the difference between the groups was the equivalent of a 6-month gap.

Noble et al. (2015) examined the cognitive and language skills of infants from diverse SES backgrounds at ages 9, 15, and 21 months to pinpoint the emergence of SES-based language disparities. They found differences in receptive vocabulary by 15 months and in expressive vocabulary by 21 months; indicating that children of parents with higher education levels had higher language skills than their peers before their second birthdays. They also found environmental factors such as parental warmth uniquely mediated the relationship between SES and language ability but not the relationship between SES and other cognitive tasks. This finding suggests that language may be more susceptible to environmental factors than other cognitive tasks.

Altogether, these studies highlight that SES disparities in children's language abilities are evident in the very first years of life, and are consistently found across different measures of SES and language skills. Despite the robustness and consistency of these findings, it is important to bear in mind individual differences, and being born into a low-income family does not guarantee a child will develop poor language skills. Many factors mediate the relationship between SES and language development.

4 This measure uses a combination of education, occupation, sex, and marital status to create a composite score for family SES (see Hollingshead, 2011).

Mediators of the relationship between early language development and SES

The home language environment significantly shapes children's language development, encompassing factors such as the quantity, quality, and complexity of language exposure (Brito, 2017). Children from low SES homes have a less enriched home language environment in all these dimensions (Brito, 2017; Fernald et al., 2013; Hart & Risley, 1995; Hoff, 2003; 2006). In their landmark study, Hart and Risley (1995) recorded the number of words addressed to children in one-hour monthly observations over two years and compared the output by SES level. Based on these recordings, they extrapolated that by the age of four, children from higher SES homes heard approximately 30 million more words than their peers from less advantaged homes, which contributed to differences in the children's vocabulary.

The 30-million-word gap study has sparked subsequent replication studies and became a source of debate (Dailey & Bergelson, 2022; Golinkoff et al., 2019; Sperry et al., 2019). Replication studies supported the notion of the 30-million-word gap and found that parents' speech mediated the relationship between SES and language development (Hoff, 2003; Huttenlocher et al., 2010). The term *30-million-word-gap* suggests that policy should prioritize increasing speech exposure for disadvantaged children, leading to the implementation of many programs in the United States (Dailey & Bergelson, 2022; Sperry et al., 2019). However, subsequent research has clarified that simply increasing the quantity of speech exposure is insufficient for improving language development. What really matters is language quality, which includes rich vocabulary, complex sentences, and child-directed speech (Cartmill et al., 2013; Golinkoff et al., 2019; Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2015; Hoff, 2003; Huttenlocher et al., 2010; Rowe, 2008; 2012). For example, one study found maternal speech quality fully accounted for SES-based differences in their young children's (16–31 months old) expressive vocabulary (Hoff, 2003).

Research on the home language environment emphasizes the vulnerability of language skills and how optimal environments foster rich language development, while environments with lower levels of conversation, social engagement, and shared reading contribute to poorer language skills. How parents talk to their children shapes their language development. In addition to measures of speech quality and quantity, other aspects of parent-child interaction, such as the use of gestures, can play important roles in developing

language (Perkins et al., 2013; Raviv et al., 2004; Rowe, 2012; Rowe & Goldin-Meadow, 2009). Early gesture use can be a good indicator of imminent verbal skills in very young children and point to early SES disparities.

Another characteristic of the home language environment is the alignment of the primary language spoken at home with the prevalent local language. In the context of the United States, households where English is not the primary language spoken are often associated with low family SES, posing an additional risk factor for toddlers' language skills (Halle et al., 2009). Bilingual children typically exhibit lower scores in receptive vocabulary than monolingual children, however, bilingualism offers other cognitive benefits, such as improved executive functions (Bialystok, 2017; Bialystok et al., 2010). When considering family SES and bilingualism separately, higher SES is associated with better performance in language and executive function tasks, while bilingualism is associated with poor performance in language and better performance in executive functions (Bialystok & Shorbagi, 2021). The interacting relationship between family SES and bilingualism in developing language is less researched than each factor independently. There is concern that the co-occurrence of low family SES and bilingualism can doubly disadvantage children, however, the limited available findings are mixed. Some studies have found a significant interaction, while others have not (Bialystok & Shorbagi, 2021; Brito et al., 2018; Calvo & Bialystok, 2014). Notably, no studies conducted to date have examined these relationships in the first years of life, leaving the current findings inconclusive.

There is also evidence of within-SES variability in home language environment measures (Pace et al., 2017). Hirsh-Pasek et al. (2015) examined how communication quality amongst mother-child dyads at age two predicted expressive language at age three within a sample of low-income families. They found that measures of dyadic communication quality were more powerful predictors of expressive language than the number of maternal words. Another study of mother-child dyads from predominantly low-SES families found that maternal speech quality when their children were 18 months old predicted vocabulary and speed of lexical access at 24 months, suggesting that, beyond vocabulary, maternal speech quality can also influence their children's verbal processing skills (Hurtado et al., 2008). These findings demonstrate the variability of interactions within low-income families and suggest that the quality of parent-child interactions can be a source of resilience for disadvantaged children's developing language.

Preliteracy, such as early shared reading in early childhood, is important for language development and later academic achievement (Dickinson et al., 2012; Zivan & Horowitz-Kraus, 2020). Children with illiterate parents may have slower language development than their peers (Fernald et al., 2006). Interestingly, Shahaieian et al. (2018) found that the relationship between early shared reading and later academic achievement was stronger among children from low-SES homes than for children from high-SES homes. This may be because children from high SES homes have other factors that contribute positively to academic achievement, decreasing the salience of shared reading. Nonetheless, it also serves as a protective factor that can buffer the effects of family SES for at-risk children.

In addition to the number of books, other material differences in the home environment, such as the availability of cognitively stimulating toys and learning materials, can also mediate the relationship between SES and early language development (Gershoff et al., 2007; Pace et al., 2017; Rodriguez et al., 2009). Lurie et al. (2021) found that cognitive stimulation at home longitudinally mediated the relationship between SES and language skills in 5–6-year-old children. Similarly, evidence from the OECD International Early Learning Survey showed that by the age of five, disadvantaged children were already lagging behind their peers in emerging literacy skills. However, the data also indicated that the gap could narrow if certain conditions were met within the home environment or if parental behaviors promoted these skills (e.g., back-and-forth conversation, reading by parents, socioemotional skills, number of books), see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Disadvantaged children can achieve equity with advantaged children

Source: Phair, 2022

In addition to language environments, different parenting styles can encourage or inhibit children’s developing language (Hoff & Laursen, 2019). Parents in lower SES homes are more likely to adopt a more authoritarian, punishment-focused parenting style, while higher SES parents tend towards higher sensitivity and positive regard (Hoff & Laursen, 2019; Lareau, 2018; Lugo-Gil & Tamis-LeMonda, 2008; Perkins et al., 2013). A large-scale study in the United States found that maternal sensitivity, based on a composite score of hostility, supportiveness, and respect for autonomy, partially mediated the relationships between SES and three-year-old expressive and receptive language ability (Raviv et al., 2004). Conversely, research on parenting strategies found mothers who used high levels of negative control had children who spoke in shorter, less diverse sentences compared to their peers (Taylor et al., 2009).

Research has also investigated the influence of the language environment in daycare facilities. Daycare centers that ranked high in language development practices, such as helping children understand and use language, and incorporating books, contributed to the vocabulary development of the attending children and predicted their vocabulary in kindergarten, even when controlling for vocabulary at age three (Hansen & Broekhuizen, 2021). One study examined whether preschool education could close SES gaps in young

children's vocabulary and found that although preschool attendance positively influenced the vocabulary of children from low SES homes, it did not close the gap (Becker, 2011). Taken together, these findings suggest that children from low-SES homes who receive more cognitive stimulation at home, and higher quality interactions with their caregivers at home and daycare, can overcome gaps in language development.

The role of stress

Exposure to chronic stress is another differentiator between children from low- and high-SES homes that can impact language development (Bradley & Corwyn, 2002; Farah, 2017; Merz et al., 2019; Noble & Giebler, 2020). Increased cortisol levels in response to chronic stress can contribute to neurocognitive differences between children from different SES backgrounds (Merz et al., 2019). Brain imaging research has found that areas associated with language are one of the main sources of neurocognitive differences between SES groups (Farah, 2017; Farah et al., 2006; Noble et al., 2012; Noble & Farah, 2013; Perkins et al., 2013). Similar to the findings regarding SES and early language development, increased stress has also been associated with lower language skills in children as young as two years old (Magill-Evans & Harrison, 2001; Noel et al., 2008). The frequent co-occurrence of stress with low SES suggests they both play a role in developing language.

Research from the Baby's First Years project found that increased stress among low-income families was associated with fewer language milestones among one-year-olds (Troller-Renfree et al., 2022). Similarly, data from the Kids in Columbus Study measured poverty and stress at 4–7 months and then language skills when the children were two years old (Justice et al., 2019). They found children from poverty-stricken homes performed poorly in expressive and receptive language, and caregiver-child interactions and maternal distress contributed to their language skills.

Summary

Language plays a crucial role in communication, and early language skills are pivotal predictors of academic success. Research has consistently found that SES-based gaps in language skills emerge in the second year of life, and these gaps set different trajectories for emerging language that influence later school and life success. However, the influence on language development does not

seem to stem from low SES or family income. Instead, environmental factors associated with low SES such as the home language environment, chronic stress, and parenting styles, explain most of the observed language gap. Although the research indicates the SES language gap begins in early childhood and widens over time, it also suggests that changes in parenting practices that encourage language development amongst disadvantaged children can close these gaps.

Early motor development

Gross motor skills involve movement and control of large muscle groups, including the arms, legs, and whole-body movement. In infancy, gross motor milestones include rolling over, sitting up, pulling to stand, and walking (Sudry et al., 2022). Gross motor skills enable infants to engage in physical activities, explore their environment, and influence their long-term physical fitness and overall health (Brian et al., 2019). Fine motor skills involve the coordination and control of small muscle groups, such as the hands and fingers, enabling precise movements that require dexterity and hand-eye coordination. Early childhood fine motor milestones include grasping an object, transferring an object from one hand to another, and thumb-finger pincer grasp (Sudry et al., 2022). Fine motor skills foster independence in young children through self-care activities like self-feeding and tying shoelaces, as well as for pivotal academic tasks such as writing and nurturing creative expression through activities like drawing. Therefore, early motor skills are crucial for the developing child's physical health, emerging cognitive skills, social-emotional well-being, and laying the foundation for independence.

SES disparities in early gross motor development

In contrast to the expansive body of research on the role of family SES in shaping early language development, studies that examine the relationship between family SES and early gross motor development are more limited. This may be because early gross motor skills are rudimentary, and gaps may not become evident until motor skills become more advanced. In addition, motor development in the early years is influenced more by biological maturation and genetic factors, and after this period, it becomes influenced more by practice and opportunity related to environmental factors (Austerberry et al., 2022;

Barnett et al., 2016; Golding et al., 2014). The SES gap in motor skills is evident in preschool- and school-aged children, but differences in early childhood are less researched (Chowdhury et al., 2010; Goodway et al., 2010; Gosselin et al., 2021; Hua et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2016).

Using the Bayley Scale of Infant Development, Black et al. (2000) examined the mental, motor, and behavioral performance of children from low-income families compared to the scale's normative scores. They found infants' (<12 months) motor scores were within the normative range, while toddlers' (>12 months) scores were lower than the normative sample, suggesting the environmental influence begins in toddlerhood, not infancy. A few small-scale studies found poor object manipulation and manual exploration amongst infants from low SES homes (Clearfield et al., 2014; Tacke et al., 2015). However, due to the small sample sizes and subdivisions by age and SES in all three studies, the generalizability of these findings is limited.

A study in Bolivia tracked the relationship between family SES, anthropometric measures, health, and nutrition, and their impact on the motor development of children under the age of five (Celhay et al., 2020). They found significant differences in motor skills between children from the poorest and wealthiest quintiles at 24–36 months old but not in infancy. Fink et al. (2020) compared language and motor milestone attainment rates in infants and toddlers living in high- and low-income countries. They found significant gaps in both domains between countries with high versus low human development index scores amongst infants as young as six months, though this gap was larger for language skills than for motor skills. However, cross-cultural studies need to consider differences in local norms and practices related to expectations in motor development that can influence the timing of motor milestones (Black & Richter, 2022; Karasik & Robinson, 2022; Libertus & Smith, 2020; Valentini et al., 2022).

Although there is insufficient evidence on SES gaps in motor development in infancy, there are findings on how the home environment in early childhood can play an influential role in shaping emerging motor skills later in life. Studies that used the Affordance in the Home Environment for Motor Development — Infant Scale, a tool that assesses opportunities for motor development in the home, found that infants from higher SES homes had higher scores on the scale (Defilipo et al., 2012; Freitas et al., 2013). Access to outside space and toys that promote motor development can positively

influence motor development (Hua et al., 2016). In addition, low maternal education and family SES increases the risk of developmental coordination disorder, a neurodevelopmental condition manifested in impaired motor coordination that affects approximately 5%-6% of school-aged children (Blank, 2012; Engel-Yeger et al., 2010; Lee & Zwicker, 2021; Tran et al., 2023; Zwicker et al., 2012). While SES gaps are not consistently evident in early childhood gross motor skills, the home environment in this period can set the stage for differences in maturing motor competence later in childhood, which impacts later physical fitness and health.

SES disparities in early fine motor development

Studies that examine SES disparities in fine motor development cannot compare in scope to the research on early language gaps. However, unlike gross motor skills, there are indications that gaps are evident in the first two years of life (Comuk-Balci et al., 2016; Ye et al., 2019). Using the Ma'anshan Birth Cohort data in the Anhui Province of China, Ye et al. (2019) found that children from higher-income homes (measured during pregnancy) with parents with higher education levels had lower rates of delayed fine motor development at 18 months. In line with the previous section, they did not find a significant relationship between SES measures and gross motor skills at this age. Comuk-Balci et al. (2016) found that socioeconomic group significantly predicted performance in a battery of fine motor tasks in infants 0–24 months of age. Studies that examine the relationship between SES and performance in developmental assessments have found positive associations between infant and toddler fine motor skills and family SES (and not gross motor skills) (Koutra et al., 2012; Rubio-Codina et al., 2015). The SES disparities in fine motor skills persist throughout preschool and into school-aged children (Aiman et al., 2016; Bobbio et al., 2007).

The relationship between fine motor skills and academic achievement

Predictors of school readiness and academic achievement often emphasize skills directly linked to early learning, such as pre-reading and math skills, as well as cognitive skills like executive functions (Duncan et al., 2007). However, there is evidence that fine motor skills are a foundational predictor of school readiness and academic achievement (Cameron et al., 2012, 2016; Carlson

et al., 2013; Grissmer et al., 2010; McClelland & Cameron, 2019). In early education classroom settings, fine motor skills play a crucial role in activities such as writing, cutting, and drawing, all essential for successful learning. The skills positively correlate with hand-eye coordination and attention to detail, aiding children in navigating classroom spaces and materials effectively. Fine motor skills also require coordination between visual perception and motor movements, known as visuomotor integration, which associates with reading and math skills that also require the processing of visual symbolic stimuli (Cameron et al., 2012; Grissmer et al., 2010). Neuro-imaging research shows that fine motor skills activate similar areas in the brain to those required for executive functions and attention (the prefrontal cortex, cerebellum, and basal ganglia), supporting the relationship between these skills (Cameron et al., 2012; Grissmer et al., 2010).

Previous studies examining fine motor skills and academic achievement have predominantly included samples of children from middle SES families. Dinehart & Manfra (2013) expanded on these findings and found that fine motor skills in preschoolers from low-income families predicted their reading and math scores in second grade, even after controlling for demographic variables, as well as early language, numeracy, and cognitive skills. Using the Early Childhood Longitudinal Study Kindergarten cohort data (ECLS-K),⁵ Potter et al. (2013) found that kindergartners from high-SES families exhibited more advanced fine motor skills than their peers, a portion of which was explained by measures of family resources such as the educational home environment. These differences in fine motor skills explained part of the SES gap in reading, math, and general knowledge tasks, demonstrating how family circumstances can influence access to stimulating activities that facilitate fine motor skills related to subsequent cognitive development.

The embodied cognition theory supports the link between cognition and motor skills, illustrating how cognitive processes are influenced and molded by the physical context of the body (Needham & Libertus, 2011; Roessingh & Bence, 2018). The cognitive-motor link is apparent in infants as they negotiate their physical surroundings, and learn to move their ever-changing bodies

5 Similar to the ECLS-B, the ECLS-K is a nationally representative sample of over 20,000 children who attended kindergarten in the U.S. in the 1998–1999 academic year and followed the children through middle school to learn about early school experiences (see: Tourangeau et al., 2005).

through goal-oriented behavior and trial and error (Adolph, 2008; Grissmer et al., 2010). Learning to grasp, sit, and walk demonstrates some of children's earliest learning achievements. In other words, motor skills teach children how to learn. Differences in early opportunities to practice fine motor skills, and access to toys and environments that encourage exploration may not yield large SES differences in early motor skills but incrementally lead to differential trajectories of these skills over time, which later contribute to gaps in motor skills and academic outcomes.

Summary

Early motor skills are the foundation for physical movement and allow children to explore their environments and gain independence. There does not seem to be an SES gap in early gross motor development; however, the research does indicate a relationship between family SES and early fine motor development. Fine motor skills are a foundational predictor of school readiness. In contrast to the breadth of research on how the SES language gap contributes to the SES achievement gap, studies on fine motor skills are more limited. Nonetheless, existing research suggests that SES disparities in fine motor skills contribute to the achievement gap, but more research is needed to confirm this.

Personal, social, and emotional development

Personal, social, and emotional (PSE) development includes multifaceted skills such as empathy, emotion regulation and understanding, sense of self, building relationships, and social competence (Darling-Churchill & Lippman, 2016). Children internalize early social and emotional interactions to form emerging competency in these skills (Rosenblum et al., 2009). At the onset, the newborn infant has immature self-regulation. The expression of emotions at this stage signals biologically based needs that evolved to alert the caregiver to provide protection and care. The infant's emotional experience quickly becomes more sophisticated. Within a few months, s/he can engage in social interactions, exhibit emotions such as sadness or anger with facial expressions, and use the caregiver's emotional cues to decide how to react in a particular circumstance. In toddlerhood, young children's skills become more advanced, and they begin to display empathy and increase their self-awareness demonstrated in emotions such as embarrassment and guilt.

Longitudinal studies have found that social and emotional skills in early childhood predict school readiness, academic achievement, and outcomes in adulthood (Denham, 2006; Jones et al., 2015; Moffitt et al., 2011). Children with higher levels of self-control during early childhood had greater outcomes than their peers with lower self-control in adulthood in terms of better physical health, lower levels of substance abuse, higher SES, and lower rates of criminal offenses (Moffitt et al., 2011). Similarly, kindergarteners who demonstrated greater socioemotional skills fared better than their peers in those areas as well (Jones et al., 2015).

Despite the importance of PSE skills, there is a lack of consensus regarding its theoretical conceptualization, resulting in inconsistent measuring techniques since each tool will focus on different aspects based on what that approach considers important (Campbell et al., 2016; Darling-Churchill & Lippman, 2016; Halle & Darling-Churchill, 2016; Jones et al., 2016; Riser et al., 2022). The Bayley socioemotional subscale has a greater focus on sensory processing, while the Ages and Stages subscale looks more at emotions and acting out behavior (Krijnen et al., 2021). The THIS scale includes personal-social milestones (e.g., smiles responsively; responds when addressed by name) and does not include emotional milestones (Sudry et al., 2022). Other studies use measures of maladjustment, problem behaviors, and externalizing and internalizing behaviors as indicators of poor PSE well-being. Some studies that examine PSE in infants assess temperament and attachment (McIntosh et al., 2021). Due to the wide breadth of PSE competencies, it is difficult to draw conclusions on research findings under the umbrella of PSE development since each study will focus on one isolated aspect of PSE skills depending on its approach or measurement method (Jones et al., 2016).

Another challenge in measuring PSE is that there is a greater element of subjectivity compared to other developmental domains. Parent reports are a methodological dilemma for all domains, but even more so for PSE because there is a higher element of subjectivity. For example, an item from the Brief Infant-Toddler Social Emotional Assessment (BITSEA; Briggs-Gowan et al., 2004) is: "My child seems nervous, tense, or fearful," to which the parent needs to select the appropriate answer (0 = not true/ rarely, 1 = somewhat true/sometimes, 2 = very true/often). The answer can reflect the parent's appraisal of what is considered nervous behavior, cultural differences regarding these emotions, and even the recent context of the infant's mood on that given day

(Campbell et al., 2016; Fernald et al., 2009; Jones et al., 2016; Yates et al., 2008). PSE skills are important for healthy emotional well-being and life course outcomes; however, one needs caution when interpreting their findings.

SES disparities in PSE development

Studies that examined the SES gap in early childhood developmental assessments have found more modest effect sizes for gaps in socioemotional development compared to the more robust differences in early language (Abufhele et al., 2022; Halle et al., 2009; Richards et al., 2018; Rubio-Codina et al., 2015; Vásquez-Echeverría et al., 2022). Rubio-Codina et al. (2015) found evidence of the gap as early as 6 months using the Bayley III scale, which widened over time. Using a nationally representative sample in Uruguay, Alvarez-Nuñez et al. (2020) examined SES differences in socioemotional development using the Ages and Stages questionnaire. They found children from low-income homes had poorer socioemotional skills than their peers by the age of 18 months. Similarly, Koutra et al. (2012) found maternal education related to socioemotional skills among 18-month-olds. The study using the ECLS-B data compared infants from low- and high-income families at 9 and 24 months in social-emotional development and found a small difference at nine months and a moderate effect size at 24 months (Halle et al., 2009).

Wolf et al. (2021) mapped social-emotional development in children four to seven years old and characterized two groups based on the rate of development. The low-growth group initially lagged behind their peers in the normative growth group and continued to develop social-emotional competency at a slower pace. Children living in poverty were more likely to be in the low-growth group. Using ECLS-K data, Fletcher & Wolfe (2016) found a relationship between family income and socioemotional skills (measured by approaches to learning, interpersonal skills, and self-control) among kindergarteners, such that children from lower-income families had poorer socioemotional skills. The gap in these skills between children from low- and high-income families doubled by fifth grade. Throughout childhood, children from low SES homes are at greater risk of developing psychopathology and poor mental health outcomes (Golberstein et al., 2016; Peverill et al., 2021). These findings suggest a modest gap in socioemotional skills emerges in the first two years of life, which appears to widen throughout childhood. However, the inconsistencies between studies regarding the emergence of the gap, and

small effect sizes may be attributed to measurement issues discussed in the previous section.

The role of stress and parenting style on PSE

Stress in the home can contribute to the impact of poverty in early childhood on developing PSE skills. Research from the Baby's First Years project found that increased stress among low-income families was associated with poorer socioemotional development amongst one-year-olds, demonstrating the cumulative risk of poverty and stress on children's developmental outcomes (Troller-Renfree et al., 2022). The increased levels of stress in low-income families can contribute to less emotional resources for parenting and harsher parenting styles (Conger & Donnellan, 2007). Differences in parenting style by SES group can influence PSE development since positive parenting practices such as acceptance and warmth, which are associated with high SES parents, positively relate to PSE competency, and harsher parenting styles, which are associated with low SES parents, adversely affect these skills (Conger & Donnellan, 2007; Cui et al., 2018; Emmen et al., 2013; Hoff & Laursen, 2019; Lugo-Gil & Tamis-LeMonda, 2008; Perkins et al., 2013). Examination of the cumulative risk factors for externalizing and internalizing behaviors among young children growing up in low-income families found that nurturing and involved parenting can overcome some of the negative risk factors (Trentacosta et al., 2008).

Summary

PSE skills allow children to process their emotions, gain a sense of self, and build relationships. Since these skills are wide-ranging and have an element of subjectivity, they are more challenging to assess in early childhood. The findings point to an SES gap in PSE skills in early childhood; however, the emergence of the gap depends on the assessment tool used. Future research should comprehensively examine the SES gap in PSE development using multiple assessment tools to fully understand how these crucial skills impact children from disadvantaged backgrounds and the long-term consequences on their future mental health and well-being.

General discussion

This review revealed that developing language is more vulnerable to the effects of family SES than other developmental domains. Research has consistently found SES-based gaps in multiple language tasks before children reach their second birthday, and these gaps widen over time and contribute to the education achievement gap. In contrast, the research on fine motor and PSE skills is less expansive. Fewer studies specifically examine fine motor skills, and PSE research has psychometric issues and theoretical inconsistency. Nonetheless, the findings suggest the SES gap is also evident in the early years in fine motor and PSE skills. Unlike the other domains, the evidence does not point to an SES gap in early gross motor skills, suggesting that early gross motor skills are less vulnerable to environmental factors in the early years and are more biologically determined. The pattern of a substantial early SES gap in language, followed by a more moderate gap in PSE and fine motor skills, and no SES differences in gross motor skills, has been replicated in multiple studies conducted in different countries (Koutra et al., 2012; Playford et al., 2017; Potijk et al., 2013; Richards et al., 2018; Rubio-Codina et al., 2015; Vásquez-Echeverría et al., 2022).

The interplay between heritable traits and environmental influences has been a classic question in the nurture versus nature debate. Several of the findings presented in this review, such as the influence of the home language environment and affordances in the home, suggest that primarily environmental factors mediate the relationship between family SES and child outcomes. However, these studies did not consider the role of genetics. One method to examine the respective contribution of genes and family SES on child development uses maternal IQ as a proxy for maternal genetic influence. Ronfani et al. (2015) aimed to understand the different contributing roles of maternal IQ, family SES, and the home environment on cognitive, language, and motor development at 18 months of age. Consistent with the collected findings presented in this review, they did not find a direct or indirect relationship between family SES and gross motor skills. They found that both maternal IQ and family SES were related to cognitive and language skills. However, adding a measure of the home environment into the model completely mediated these relationships, demonstrating how the home environment is a more influential factor over family SES and maternal IQ on early cognition and language.

The gold standard experimental paradigm that aims to attribute the unique contributions of genetic and environmental influences is twin studies that can provide separate estimates for each component. A meta-analysis of 139 twin studies, including a sample of over 79,000 pairs of monozygotic twins, assessed estimates for heritability and environmental influence of psychological traits and developmental milestones in the first two years of life (Austerberry et al., 2022). It found that motor development had the strongest association with genetic factors, whereas language development had the strongest association with environmental factors in the first two years of life. Although this study did not include a measure of family SES, its conclusion aligns with the findings of this review: Early language skills are strongly influenced by the child's environment, whereas early gross motor skills are less susceptible to environmental influences.

Children are not embarking on life at the same starting line: family SES creates disparities from the very beginning of early childhood development that have long-term ramifications on life-course outcomes. If we want to rectify SES disparities in education, health, and the labor market, we need to first address poverty in early childhood to interrupt the trajectory and give every child the opportunity to actualize their full potential. Reviewing how these disparities unfold in early childhood by developmental domain has revealed that despite the pervasive effects of family SES, the degree of impact varies by the vulnerability of different developmental areas to environmental factors during this period.

Bringing it together: Early childhood in Israel

Understanding the relationship between family SES and early childhood development and how it influences life course outcomes is crucial for Israel, not only because of the large percentage of young children in the population but also due to the high poverty rates among children. Approximately a third of Israeli children under the age of four live in households below the poverty line (Navon & Bowers, 2023). This finding, in conjunction with the collected findings of this review, should raise a concern that a substantial proportion of young Israeli children may be at risk of delayed development, particularly in language.

Prevention in early childhood is considered an effective strategy, as it not only mitigates potential long-term societal costs, it also fosters a solid foundation that supports healthy, on-track development (Heckman, 2006). However, Israel's early childhood education and health systems lack sufficient investment, hindering equitable access to quality services and perpetuating socioeconomic disparities. Access to high-quality early childhood education is crucial for leveling the playing field and fostering language, cognitive, and socioemotional development during formative years (Vandenbroeck, 2020). Specific measures of the language environment in daycare centers, including helping children understand and use language, and teaching with books, have been found to predict children's vocabulary in kindergarten, even when controlling for their vocabulary at age three (Hansen & Broekhuizen, 2021). However, Israel's ECEC system falls short in terms of quality, affordability, and accessibility, requiring comprehensive improvements as proposed in a previous position paper (Blank & Silverman, 2022).

Tipat Halav has the potential to be a cutting-edge resource for preventative health services since most families visit the clinics for vaccinations. However, this resource has not been fully utilized since the National Health Insurance Law was implemented in 1995, which placed the responsibility of Tipat Halav in limbo between the health funds and the Ministry of Health. The lack of a clear, regulatory mechanism has impeded further investment in the system, stalling much-needed updates in staffing, salaries, and services. While developmental surveillance services are provided in the Tipat Halav clinic to identify children at risk of delayed development, follow-up assessments and subsequent health services (e.g., speech therapy) are provided elsewhere, complicating the continuity of care. Increasing investment and developmental services provided at Tipat Halav would ease the accessibility of health services to all children and increase the likelihood of on-track development regardless of family background.

References

- Abufhele, A., Contreras, D., Puentes, E., Telias, A., & Valdebenito, N. (2022). [Socioeconomic gradients in child development: Evidence from a Chilean longitudinal study 2010–2017](#). *Advances in Life Course Research*, *52*, 100451.
- Acharya, K., Rahman, M. S., Islam, M. R., Gilmour, S., Dhungel, B., Parajuli, R. P., Nishimura, T., Senju, A., & Tsuchiya, K. J. (2023). [Socioeconomic and education-based inequality in suspected developmental delays among Nepalese children: A subnational level assessment](#). *Scientific Reports*, *13*(1).
- Adolph, K. E. (2008). [Learning to move](#). *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, *17*(3), 213–218.
- Ahishakiye, A., Abimana, M. C., Beck, K., Miller, A. C., Betancourt, T. S., Magge, H., Mutaganzwa, C., & Kirk, C. M. (2019). [Developmental outcomes of preterm and low birth weight toddlers and term peers in Rwanda](#). *Annals of Global Health*, *85*(1), 147, 1–11.
- Ahmadi Doulabi, M., Sajedi, F., Vameghi, R., Mazaheri, M. A., & Akbarzadeh Baghban, A. (2017). Socioeconomic status index to interpret inequalities in child development. *Iranian Journal of Child Neurology*, *11*(2), 13–25.
- Aiman, S., Yusof, S. Md., Kadir, Z. A., & Sabturani, N. (2016). [The relationship between socioeconomic status and fine motor skills among six-year-old preschool children](#). In S. I. Ismail, N. Sulaiman, & R. Adnan (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2nd international colloquium on sports science, exercise, engineering and technology 2015* (pp. 141–148). Springer.
- Alloway, T. P., & Alloway, R. G. (2010). [Investigating the predictive roles of working memory and IQ in academic attainment](#). *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, *106*(1), 20–29.
- Álvarez-Nuñez, L., González, M., Rudnitzky, F., & Vásquez-Echeverría, A. (2020). [Psychometric properties of the Spanish version of the Ages & Stages Questionnaires: Social–Emotional in a nationally representative sample](#). *Early Human Development*, *149*, 105157.
- Andreassen, C., & Fletcher, P. (2007). *Early childhood longitudinal study, birth cohort (ECLS–B) psychometric report for the 2-year data collection*. National Center for Education Statistics, Institute of Education Sciences, U.S. Department of Education.
- Arriaga, R. I., Fenson, L., Cronan, T., & Pethick, S. J. (1998). [Scores on the MacArthur Communicative Development Inventory of children from low- and middle-income families](#). *Applied Psycholinguistics*, *19*(2), 209–223.

- Austerberry, C., Mateen, M., Fearon, P., & Ronald, A. (2022). [Heritability of psychological traits and developmental milestones in infancy: A systematic review and meta-analysis](#). *JAMA Network Open*, *5*(8), e2227887.
- Bailey, D. B. (2001). *Critical thinking about critical periods* (pp. xiv, 299). Paul H Brookes Publishing.
- Ball, R. S. (1977). [The Gesell developmental schedules: Arnold Gesell \(1880–1961\)](#). *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, *5*(3), 233–239.
- Barnett, L. M., Lai, S. K., Veldman, S. L. C., Hardy, L. L., Cliff, D. P., Morgan, P. J., Zask, A., Lubans, D. R., Shultz, S. P., Ridgers, N. D., Rush, E., Brown, H. L., & Okely, A. D. (2016). [Correlates of gross motor competence in children and adolescents: A systematic review and meta-analysis](#). *Sports Medicine (Auckland, N.Z.)*, *46*(11), 1663–1688.
- Becker, B. (2011). [Social disparities in children’s vocabulary in early childhood. Does pre-school education help to close the gap?](#) *The British Journal of Sociology*, *62*(1), 69–88.
- Bello, A. I., Quartey, J. N., & Appiah, L. A. (2013). [Screening for developmental delay among children attending a rural community welfare clinic in Ghana](#). *BMC Pediatrics*, *13*(1), 119.
- Betancourt, L. M., Brodsky, N. L., & Hurt, H. (2015). [Socioeconomic \(SES\) differences in language are evident in female infants at 7 months of age](#). *Early Human Development*, *91*(12), 719–724.
- Bialystok, E. (2017). [The bilingual adaptation: How minds accommodate experience](#). *Psychological Bulletin*, *143*(3), 233–262.
- Bialystok, E., Luk, G., Peets, K. F., & Yang, S. (2010). [Receptive vocabulary differences in monolingual and bilingual children](#). *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, *13*(4), 525–531.
- Bialystok, E., & Shorbagi, S. H. (2021). [Subtle increments in socioeconomic status and bilingualism jointly affect children’s verbal and nonverbal performance](#). *Journal of Cognition and Development*, *22*(3), 467–490.
- Bilu, Y., Amit, G., Sudry, T., Akiva, P., Avgil Tsadok, M., Zimmerman, D. R., Baruch, R., & Sadaka, Y. (2023). [A developmental surveillance score for quantitative monitoring of early childhood milestone attainment: Algorithm development and validation](#). *JMIR Public Health and Surveillance*, *9*, e47315.
- Bishwokarma, A., Shrestha, D., Bhujel, K., Chand, N., Adhikari, L., Kaphle, M., Wagle, A., & Karmacharya, I. (2022). [Developmental delay and its associated factors among children under five years in urban slums of Nepal](#). *PLOS ONE*, *17*(2), e0263105.

- Black, M. M., Hess, C. R., & Berenson-Howard, J. (2000). Toddlers from low-income families have below normal mental, motor, and behavior scores on the revised Bayley scales. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology, 21*(6), 655–666.
- Black, M. M., & Richter, L. M. (2022). Different is not deficient: Respecting diversity in early childhood development. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health, 6*(12), e26.
- Blank, R. (2012). Information for parents and teachers on the European Academy for Childhood Disability (EACD) recommendations on Developmental Coordination Disorder. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology, 54*(11), e8–e9.
- Blossfeld, H.-P., Kulic, N., Skopek, J., & Triventi, M. (2017). *Childcare, early education and social inequality: An international perspective*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Bobbio, T. G., Morcillo, A. M., Filho, A. D. A. B., & Gonçalves, V. M. G. (2007). Factors associated with inadequate fine motor skills in Brazilian students of different socioeconomic status. *Perceptual and Motor Skills, 105*(3_suppl), 1187–1195.
- Bornstein, M. H., Hahn, C.-S., Putnick, D. L., & Suwalsky, J. T. D. (2014). Stability of core language skill from early childhood to adolescence: A latent variable approach. *Child Development, 85*(4), 1346–1356.
- Bradley, R. H., & Corwyn, R. F. (2002). Socioeconomic status and child development. *Annual Review of Psychology, 53*(1), 371–399.
- Brian, A., Pennell, A., Taunton, S., Starrett, A., Howard-Shaughnessy, C., Goodway, J. D., Wadsworth, D., Rudisill, M., & Stodden, D. (2019). Motor competence levels and developmental delay in early childhood: A multicenter cross-sectional study conducted in the USA. *Sports Medicine, 49*(10), 1609–1618.
- Brito, N. H. (2017). Influence of the home linguistic environment on early language development. *Policy Insights from the Behavioral and Brain Sciences, 4*(2), 155–162.
- Brito, N. H., Noble, K. G., & the Pediatric Imaging, G. S., Neurocognition. (2018). The independent and interacting effects of socioeconomic status and dual-language use on brain structure and cognition. *Developmental Science, 21*(6), e12688.
- Bronfenbrenner, U., & Morris, P. A. (1998). *The ecology of developmental processes*. In *Handbook of child psychology: Theoretical models of human development* (Vol. 1, 5th ed.) (pp. 993–1028). John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Brooks-Gunn, J., & Duncan, G. J. (1997). The effects of poverty on children. *The Future of Children, 7*(2), 55–71.

- Burchinal, M. R., Pace, A., Hirsh-Pasek, K., & Golinkoff, R. M. (2016). *Early language outshines other predictors of academic and social trajectories in elementary school*. Administration for Children and Families (ACF), National Research Conference on Early Childhood, Washington, DC, July 11.
- Calvo, A., & Bialystok, E. (2014). Independent effects of bilingualism and socioeconomic status on language ability and executive functioning. *Cognition*, *130*(3), 278–288.
- Cameron, C. E., Brock, L. L., Murrah, W. M., Bell, L. H., Worzalla, S. L., Grissmer, D., & Morrison, F. J. (2012). Fine motor skills and executive function both contribute to kindergarten achievement. *Child Development*, *83*(4), 1229–1244.
- Cameron, C. E., Cottone, E. A., Murrah, W. M., & Grissmer, D. W. (2016). How are motor skills linked to children's school performance and academic achievement? *Child Development Perspectives*, *10*(2), 93–98.
- Campbell, S. B., Denham, S. A., Howarth, G. Z., Jones, S. M., Whittaker, J. V., Williford, A. P., Willoughby, M. T., Yudron, M., & Darling-Churchill, K. (2016). Commentary on the review of measures of early childhood social and emotional development: Conceptualization, critique, and recommendations. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, *45*, 19–41.
- Carlson, A., Rowe, E., & Curby, T. (2013). Disentangling fine motor skills' relations to academic achievement: The relative contributions of visual-spatial integration and visual-motor coordination. *The Journal of Genetic Psychology*, *174*, 514–533.
- Cartmill, E. A., Armstrong, B. F., Gleitman, L. R., Goldin-Meadow, S., Medina, T. N., & Trueswell, J. C. (2013). Quality of early parent input predicts child vocabulary 3 years later. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *110*(28), 11278–11283.
- Celhay, P., Martinez, S., & Vidal, C. (2020). Measuring socioeconomic gaps in nutrition and early child development in Bolivia. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, *19*(1), 122.
- Chowdhury, S. D., Wrotniak, B. H., & Ghosh, T. (2010). Nutritional and socioeconomic factors in motor development of Santal children of the Purulia district, India. *Early Human Development*, *86*(12), 779–784.
- Clearfield, M. W., Bailey, L. S., Jenne, H. K., Stanger, S. B., & Tacke, N. (2014). Socioeconomic status affects oral and manual exploration across the first year. *Infant Mental Health Journal*, *35*(1), 63–69.
- Comuk-Balci, N., Bayoglu, B., Tekindal, A., Kerem-Gunel, M., & Anlar, B. (2016). Screening preschool children for fine motor skills: Environmental influence. *Journal of Physical Therapy Science*, *28*(3), 1026–1031.

- Conger, R. D., & Donnellan, M. B. (2007). [An interactionist perspective on the socioeconomic context of human development](#). *Annual Review of Psychology*, *58*(1), 175–199.
- Cui, J., Mistur, E. J., Wei, C., Lansford, J. E., Putnick, D. L., & Bornstein, M. H. (2018). [Multilevel factors affecting early socioemotional development in humans](#). *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, *72*(10), 172.
- Dailey, S., & Bergelson, E. (2022). [Language input to infants of different socioeconomic statuses: A quantitative meta-analysis](#). *Developmental Science*, *25*(3), e13192.
- Darling-Churchill, K. E., & Lippman, L. (2016). [Early childhood social and emotional development: Advancing the field of measurement](#). *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, *45*, 1–7.
- Defilipo, É. C., Frônio, J. da S., Teixeira, M. T. B., Leite, I. C. G., Bastos, R. R., Vieira, M. de T., & Ribeiro, L. C. (2012). [Opportunities in the home environment for motor development](#). *Revista de Saúde Pública*, *46*, 633–641.
- Denham, S. A. (2006). [Social-emotional competence as support for school readiness: What is it and how do we assess it?](#) *Early Education and Development*, *17*(1), 57–89.
- Dickinson, D. K., Griffith, J. A., Golinkoff, R. M., & Hirsh-Pasek, K. (2012). [How reading books fosters language development around the world](#). *Child Development Research*, *2012*, 1–15.
- Dinehart, L., & Manfra, L. (2013). [Associations between low-income children's fine motor skills in preschool and academic performance in second grade](#). *Early Education and Development*, *24*(2), 138–161.
- Duncan, G. J., Dowsett, C. J., Claessens, A., Magnuson, K., Huston, A. C., Klebanov, P., Pagani, L. S., Feinstein, L., Engel, M., Brooks-Gunn, J., Sexton, H., Duckworth, K., & Japel, C. (2007). [School readiness and later achievement](#). *Developmental Psychology*, *43*(6), 1428–1446.
- Duncan, G. J., Magnuson, K., & Votruba-Drzal, E. (2017). [Moving beyond correlations in assessing the consequences of poverty](#). *Annual Review of Psychology*, *68*(1), 413–434.
- Durham, R. E., Farkas, G., Hammer, C. S., Bruce Tomblin, J., & Catts, H. W. (2007). [Kindergarten oral language skill: A key variable in the intergenerational transmission of socioeconomic status](#). *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, *25*(4), 294–305.

- Durkin, M. S., Maenner, M. J., Meaney, F. J., Levy, S. E., DiGiuseppi, C., Nicholas, J. S., Kirby, R. S., Pinto-Martin, J. A., & Schieve, L. A. (2010). Socioeconomic inequality in the prevalence of Autism Spectrum Disorder: Evidence from a U.S. cross-sectional study. *PLOS ONE*, 5(7), e11551.
- Emerson, E., Savage, A., & Llewellyn, G. (2018). Significant cognitive delay among 3- to 4-year old children in low- and middle-income countries: Prevalence estimates and potential impact of preventative interventions. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 47(5), 1465–1474.
- Emmen, R. A. G., Malda, M., Mesman, J., van IJzendoorn, M. H., Prevoe, M. J. L., & Yeniad, N. (2013). Socioeconomic status and parenting in ethnic minority families: Testing a minority family stress model. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 27(6), 896–904.
- Engel-Yeger, B., Rosenblum, S., & Josman, N. (2010). Movement Assessment Battery for Children (M-ABC): Establishing construct validity for Israeli children. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 31(1), 87–96.
- Farah, M. J. (2017). The neuroscience of socioeconomic status: Correlates, causes, and consequences. *Neuron*, 96(1), 56–71.
- Farah, M. J., Shera, D. M., Savage, J. H., Betancourt, L., Giannetta, J. M., Brodsky, N. L., Malmud, E. K., & Hurt, H. (2006). Childhood poverty: Specific associations with neurocognitive development. *Brain Research*, 1110(1), 166–174.
- Fernald, A., Marchman, V. A., & Weisleder, A. (2013). SES differences in language processing skill and vocabulary are evident at 18 months. *Developmental Science*, 16(2), 234–248.
- Fernald, L. C. H., Kariger, P., Engle, P., & Raikes, A. (2009). *Examining early child development in low-income countries: A toolkit for the assessment of children in the first five years of life*. World Bank.
- Fernald, L. C. H., Kariger, P., Hidrobo, M., & Gertler, P. J. (2012). Socioeconomic gradients in child development in very young children: Evidence from India, Indonesia, Peru, and Senegal. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 109(Suppl 2), 17273–17280.
- Fernald, L. C., Neufeld, L. M., Barton, L. R., Schnaas, L., Rivera, J., & Gertler, P. J. (2006). Parallel deficits in linear growth and mental development in low-income Mexican infants in the second year of life. *Public Health Nutrition*, 9(2), 178–186.
- Fink, G., McCoy, D. C., & Yousafzai, A. (2020). Contextual and socioeconomic variation in early motor and language development. *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, 105(5), 421–427.

- Fletcher, J. M., & Wolfe, B. (2016). [The importance of family income in the formation and evolution of non-cognitive skills in childhood](#). *Economics of Education Review*, *54*, 143–154.
- Frank, M. C., Marchman, V. A., Yurovsky, D., & Braginsky, M. (2021). *Variability and consistency in children's language learning across languages: The Wordbank Project*. MIT Press.
- Frankenburg, W. K., Dodds, J., Archer, P., Shapiro, H., & Bresnick, B. (1992). [The Denver II: A major revision and restandardization of the Denver Developmental Screening Test](#). *Pediatrics*, *89*(1), 91–97.
- Frankenburg, W. K., & Dodds, J. B. (1967). [The Denver Developmental Screening Test](#). *The Journal of Pediatrics*, *71*(2), 181–191.
- Freitas, T. C. B., Gabbard, C., Caçola, P., Montebelo, M. I. L., & Santos, D. C. C. (2013). [Family socioeconomic status and the provision of motor affordances in the home](#). *Brazilian Journal of Physical Therapy*, *17*(4), 319–327.
- Gershoff, E. T., Aber, J. L., Raver, C. C., & Lennon, M. C. (2007). Income is not enough: Incorporating material hardship into models of income associations with parenting and child development. *Child Development*, *78*(1), 70–95.
- Gil, J. D., Ewerling, F., Ferreira, L. Z., & Barros, A. J. (2020). [Early childhood suspected developmental delay in 63 low- and middle-income countries: Large within- and between-country inequalities documented using national health surveys](#). *Journal of Global Health*, *10*(1), 010427.
- Gilmore, J. H., Knickmeyer, R. C., & Gao, W. (2018). [Imaging structural and functional brain development in early childhood](#). *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, *19*(3), Article 3.
- Golberstein, E., Gonzales, G., & Meara, E. (2016). [Economic conditions and children's mental health](#). NBER Working Paper 22459.
- Golding, J., Emmett, P., Iles-Caven, Y., Steer, C., & Lingam, R. (2014). [A review of environmental contributions to childhood motor skills](#). *Journal of Child Neurology*, *29*(11), 1531–1547.
- Golinkoff, R. M., Hoff, E., Rowe, M. L., Tamis-LeMonda, C. S., & Hirsh-Pasek, K. (2019). [Language matters: Denying the existence of the 30-million-word gap has serious consequences](#). *Child Development*, *90*(3), 985–992.
- Goodway, J. D., Robinson, L. E., & Crowe, H. (2010). [Gender differences in fundamental motor skill development in disadvantaged preschoolers from two geographical regions](#). *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, *81*(1), 17–24.

- Gosselin, V., Leone, M., & Laberge, S. (2021). Socioeconomic and gender-based disparities in the motor competence of school-age children. *Journal of Sports Sciences, 39*(3), 341–350.
- Grissmer, D., Grimm, K. J., Aiyer, S. M., Murrah, W. M., & Steele, J. S. (2010). Fine motor skills and early comprehension of the world: Two new school readiness indicators. *Developmental Psychology, 46*(5), 1008–1017.
- Grøver, V. (2017). Fostering vocabulary in early childhood education. In *The Routledge international handbook of early literacy education*. Routledge.
- Halle, T., Forry, N., Hair, E., Perper, K., Wandner, L., Wessel, J., & Vick, J. (2009). *Disparities in early learning and development: Lessons from the early childhood longitudinal study — Birth cohort (ECLS-B): (571822009-001)* [dataset]. American Psychological Association.
- Halle, T. G., & Darling-Churchill, K. E. (2016). Review of measures of social and emotional development. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology, 45*, 8–18.
- Hansen, J. E., & Broekhuizen, M. L. (2021). Quality of the language-learning environment and vocabulary development in early childhood. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research, 65*(2), 302–317.
- Hart, B., & Risley, T. R. (1995). *Meaningful differences in the everyday experience of young American children* (pp. xxiii, 268). Paul H Brookes Publishing.
- Hirsh-Pasek, K., Adamson, L. B., Bakeman, R., Owen, M. T., Golinkoff, R. M., Pace, A., Yust, P. K. S., & Suma, K. (2015). The contribution of early communication quality to low-income children's language success. *Psychological Science, 26*(7), 1071–1083.
- Hoff, E. (2003). The specificity of environmental influence: Socioeconomic status affects early vocabulary development via maternal speech. *Child Development, 74*(5), 1368–1378.
- Hoff, E. (2006). How social contexts support and shape language development. *Developmental Review, 26*(1), 55–88.
- Hoff, E. (2013). Interpreting the early language trajectories of children from low-SES and language minority homes: Implications for closing achievement gaps. *Developmental Psychology, 49*(1), 4.
- Hoff, E. (2014). *Language Development* (5th ed.). Wadsworth Cengage Learning.
- Hoff, E., & Laursen, B. (2019). Socioeconomic Status and Parenting. In *Handbook of parenting* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
- Hollingshead, A. B. (2011). Four factor index of social status. *Yale Journal of Sociology, 21*.

- Hua, J., Duan, T., Gu, G., Wo, D., Zhu, Q., Liu, J.-Q., Liu, M., Wu, Z., & Meng, W. (2016). Effects of home and education environments on children's motor performance in China. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, *58*(8), 868–876.
- Hurtado, N., Marchman, V. A., & Fernald, A. (2008). Does input influence uptake? Links between maternal talk, processing speed and vocabulary size in Spanish-learning children. *Developmental Science*, *11*(6), F31–F39.
- Huttenlocher, J., Waterfall, H., Vasilyeva, M., Vevea, J., & Hedges, L. V. (2010). Sources of variability in children's language growth. *Cognitive Psychology*, *61*(4), 343–365.
- Jin, H., Hua, J., Shen, J., Feng, L., & Gu, G. (2016). Status and determinants of motor impairment in preschool children from migrant families in China. *Iranian Journal of Pediatrics*, *26*(5), e5427.
- Johnson, S. B., Raghunathan, R. S., Li, M., Nair, D., & Matson, P. A. (2022). Moving up but not getting ahead: Family socioeconomic position in pregnancy, social mobility, and child cognitive development in the first seven years of life. *SSM — Population Health*, *17*, 101064.
- Johnson, S. B., Riis, J. L., & Noble, K. G. (2016). State of the art review: Poverty and the developing brain. *Pediatrics*, *137*(4), e20153075.
- Jones, D. E., Greenberg, M., & Crowley, M. (2015). Early social-emotional functioning and public health: The relationship between kindergarten social competence and future wellness. *American Journal of Public Health*, *105*(11), 2283–2290.
- Jones, S. M., Zaslow, M., Darling-Churchill, K. E., & Halle, T. G. (2016). Assessing early childhood social and emotional development: Key conceptual and measurement issues. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, *45*, 42–48.
- Justice, L. M., Jiang, H., Purtell, K. M., Schmeer, K., Boone, K., Bates, R., & Salsberry, P. J. (2019). Conditions of poverty, parent–child interactions, and toddlers' early language skills in low-income families. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, *23*(7), 971–978.
- Karasik, L. B., & Robinson, S. R. (2022). Milestones or millstones: How standard assessments mask cultural variation and misinform policies aimed at early childhood development. *Policy Insights from the Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, *9*(1), 57–64.
- Koutra, K., Chatzi, L., Roumeliotaki, T., Vassilaki, M., Giannakopoulou, E., Batsos, C., Koutis, A., & Kogevinas, M. (2012). Socio-demographic determinants of infant neurodevelopment at 18 months of age: Mother–Child Cohort (Rhea Study) in Crete, Greece. *Infant Behavior and Development*, *35*(1), 48–59.

- Krijnen, L. J. G., Verhoeven, M., & van Baar, A. L. (2021). [Assessing social-emotional development in infants and toddlers using parent-reports: Comparing the ASQ-SE-NL to the Social-Emotional Scale of the Bayley-III-NL](#). *Early Human Development*, *161*, 105439.
- Lareau, A. (2018). Unequal childhoods: Class, race, and family life. In *Inequality in the 21st century*. Routledge.
- Lee, E. J., & Zwicker, J. G. (2021). [Early identification of children with/at risk of developmental coordination disorder: A scoping review](#). *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, *63*(6), 649–658.
- Lee, V. E., & Burkam, D. T. (2002). *Inequality at the starting gate: Social background differences in achievement as children begin school*. Economic Policy Institute.
- Lejarraga, H. (2012). [Growth in infancy and childhood: A pediatric approach](#) (Chapter 2). In N. Cameron & B. Bogin (Eds.), *Human growth and development* (2nd ed.) (pp. 23–56). Academic Press.
- Libertus, K., & Smith, D. K. (2020). [Milestones: Physical development from birth to age 3](#). In *Encyclopedia of infant and early childhood development* (pp. 339–346). Elsevier.
- Lu, C., Black, M. M., & Richter, L. M. (2016). [Risk of poor development in young children in low-income and middle-income countries: An estimation and analysis at the global, regional, and country level](#). *The Lancet Global Health*, *4*(12), e916–e922.
- Lugo-Gil, J., & Tamis-LeMonda, C. S. (2008). Family resources and parenting quality: Links to children’s cognitive development across the first 3 years. *Child Development*, *79*(4), 1065–1085.
- Magill-Evans, J., & Harrison, M. J. (2001). [Parent-child interactions, parenting stress, and developmental outcomes at 4 years](#). *Children’s Health Care*, *30*(2), 135–150.
- Marks, G. N., Cresswell, J., & Ainley, J. (2006). [Explaining socioeconomic inequalities in student achievement: The role of home and school factors](#). *Educational Research and Evaluation*, *12*(2), 105–128.
- McClelland, M. M., & Cameron, C. E. (2019). [Developing together: The role of executive function and motor skills in children’s early academic lives](#). *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, *46*, 142–151.
- McIntosh, J. E., Olsson, C. A., Schuijers, M., Tan, E. S., Painter, F., Schnabel, A., LeBas, G., Higgs-Howarth, S., Benstead, M., Booth, A. T., & Hutchinson, D. (2021). [Exploring perinatal indicators of infant social-emotional development: A review of the replicated evidence](#). *Clinical Child and Family Psychology Review*, *24*(3), 450–483.

- Merz, E. C., Desai, P. M., Maskus, E. A., Melvin, S. A., Rehman, R., Torres, S. D., Meyer, J., He, X., & Noble, K. G. (2019). Socioeconomic disparities in chronic physiologic stress are associated with brain structure in children. *Biological Psychiatry, 86*(12), 921–929.
- Merz, E. C., Maskus, E. A., Melvin, S. A., He, X., & Noble, K. G. (2020). Socioeconomic disparities in language input are associated with children's language-related brain structure and reading skills. *Child Development, 91*(3), 846–860.
- Moffitt, T. E., Arseneault, L., Belsky, D., Dickson, N., Hancox, R. J., Harrington, H., Houts, R., Poulton, R., Roberts, B. W., Ross, S., Sears, M. R., Thomson, W. M., & Caspi, A. (2011). A gradient of childhood self-control predicts health, wealth, and public safety. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 108*(7), 2693–2698.
- Needham, A., & Libertus, K. (2011). Embodiment in early development. *WIREs Cognitive Science, 2*(1), 117–123.
- Nelson, C. A., Zeanah, C. H., & Fox, N. A. (2019). How early experience shapes human development: The case of psychosocial deprivation. *Neural Plasticity, 2019*, e1676285.
- Noble, K. G., Engelhardt, L. E., Brito, N. H., Mack, L. J., Nail, E. J., Angal, J., Barr, R., Fifer, W. P., & Elliott, A. J. (2015). Socioeconomic disparities in neurocognitive development in the first two years of life. *Developmental Psychobiology, 57*(5), 535–551.
- Noble, K. G., & Farah, M. J. (2013). Neurocognitive consequences of socioeconomic disparities: The intersection of cognitive neuroscience and public health. *Developmental Science, 16*(5), 639–640.
- Noble, K. G., Farah, M. J., & McCandliss, B. D. (2006). Socioeconomic background modulates cognition–achievement relationships in reading. *Cognitive Development, 21*(3), 349–368.
- Noble, K. G., & Giebler, M. (2020). The neuroscience of socioeconomic inequality. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences, 6*.
- Noble, K. G., Houston, S. M., Kan, E., & Sowell, E. R. (2012). Neural correlates of socioeconomic status in the developing human brain. *Developmental Science, 15*(4), 516–527.
- Noel, M., Peterson, C., & Jesso, B. (2008). The relationship of parenting stress and child temperament to language development among economically disadvantaged preschoolers. *Journal of Child Language, 35*(4), 823–843.

- Nowell, K. P., Brewton, C. M., Allain, E., & Mire, S. S. (2015). [The influence of demographic factors on the identification of Autism Spectrum Disorder: A review and call for research](#). *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, *2*(3), 300–309.
- Pace, A., Luo, R., Hirsh-Pasek, K., & Golinkoff, R. M. (2017). [Identifying pathways between socioeconomic status and language development](#). *Annual Review of Linguistics*, *3*(1), 285–308.
- Perkins, S. C., Finegood, E. D., & Swain, J. E. (2013). Poverty and language development: Roles of parenting and stress. *Innovations in Clinical Neuroscience*, *10*(4), 10–19.
- Peterson, R. L., & Pennington, B. F. (2015). [Developmental Dyslexia](#). *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, *11*(1), 283–307.
- Peverill, M., Dirks, M. A., Narvaja, T., Herts, K. L., Comer, J. S., & McLaughlin, K. A. (2021). [Socioeconomic status and child psychopathology in the United States: A meta-analysis of population-based studies](#). *Clinical Psychology Review*, *83*, 101933.
- Phair, R. (2022). [How can equity in children's early learning be achieved?](#) OECD Education and Skills Today, October 26.
- Phillips, D., & Shonkoff, J. (Eds.). (2000). *From neurons to neighborhoods: The science of early childhood development*. National Academies Press.
- Playford, C. J., Dibben, C., & Williamson, L. (2017). [Socioeconomic disadvantage, fetal environment and child development: Linked Scottish administrative records based study](#). *International Journal for Equity in Health*, *16*(1), 203.
- Potijk, M. R., Kerstjens, J. M., Bos, A. F., Reijneveld, S. A., & de Winter, A. F. (2013). [Developmental delay in moderately preterm-born children with low socioeconomic status: Risks multiply](#). *The Journal of Pediatrics*, *163*(5), 1289–1295.
- Potter, D., Mashburn, A., & Grissmer, D. (2013). [The family, neuroscience, and academic skills: An interdisciplinary account of social class gaps in children's test scores](#). *Social Science Research*, *42*(2), 446–464.
- Provence, S., Erikson, J., Vater, S., & Palmeri, S. (1995). *Infant-toddler developmental assessment: IDA*. Riverside Publishing Company.
- Rai, D., Lewis, G., Lundberg, M., Araya, R., Svensson, A., Dalman, C., Carpenter, P., & Magnusson, C. (2012). [Parental socioeconomic status and risk of offspring Autism Spectrum Disorders in a Swedish population-based study](#). *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, *51*(5), 467–476.e6.

- Raviv, T., Kessenich, M., & Morrison, F. J. (2004). A mediational model of the association between socioeconomic status and three-year-old language abilities: The role of parenting factors. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly, 19*(4), 528–547.
- Ribeiro, L. A., Zachrisson, H. D., Nærde, A., Wang, M. V., Brandlistuen, R. E., & Passaretta, G. (2023). Socioeconomic disparities in early language development in two Norwegian samples. *Applied Developmental Science, 27*(2), 172–188.
- Richards, B., Bacon-Shone, J., & Rao, N. (2018). Socioeconomic correlates of early child development: Gradients from six countries in the East Asia-Pacific region. *International Journal of Behavioral Development, 42*(6), 581–587.
- Riser, Q. H., Rouse, H. L., & Dorius, C. J. (2022). Family income trajectories and early child development: A latent class growth analysis. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology, 83*, 101469.
- Rodriguez, E. T., Tamis-LeMonda, C. S., Spellmann, M. E., Pan, B. A., Raikes, H., Lugo-Gil, J., & Luze, G. (2009). The formative role of home literacy experiences across the first three years of life in children from low-income families. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology, 30*(6), 677–694.
- Roessingh, H., & Bence, M. (2018). Embodied cognition: Laying the foundation for early language and literacy learning. *Language and Literacy, 20*(4), Article 4.
- Ronfani, L., Vecchi Brumatti, L., Mariuz, M., Tognin, V., Bin, M., Ferluga, V., Knowles, A., Montico, M., & Barbone, F. (2015). The complex interaction between home environment, socioeconomic status, maternal IQ and early child neurocognitive development: A multivariate analysis of data collected in a newborn cohort study. *PLOS ONE, 10*(5), e0127052.
- Rosenblum, K. L., Dayton, C. J., & Muzik, M. (2009). Infant social and emotional development: The emergence of self in a relational context. *Handbook of Infant Mental Health, 3*, 80–103.
- Rowe, M. L. (2008). Child-directed speech: Relation to socioeconomic status, knowledge of child development and child vocabulary skill. *Journal of Child Language, 35*(1), 185–205.
- Rowe, M. L. (2012). A longitudinal investigation of the role of quantity and quality of child-directed speech in vocabulary development. *Child Development, 83*(5), 1762–1774.
- Rowe, M. L., & Goldin-Meadow, S. (2009). Differences in early gesture explain SES disparities in child vocabulary size at school entry. *Science, 323*(5916), 951–953.

- Rowe, M. L., Raudenbush, S. W., & Goldin-Meadow, S. (2012). [The pace of vocabulary growth helps predict later vocabulary skill](#). *Child Development, 83*(2), 508–525.
- Rubio-Codina, M., Attanasio, O., Meghir, C., Varela, N., & Grantham-McGregor, S. (2015). [The socioeconomic gradient of child development: Cross-sectional evidence from children 6–42 months in Bogota](#). *The Journal of Human Resources, 50*(2), 464–483.
- Scarborough, H. S. (2009). Connecting early language and literacy to later reading (dis)abilities: Evidence, theory, and practice. In *Approaching difficulties in literacy development: Assessment, pedagogy and programmes*. SAGE Publications.
- Schelbe, L., Pryce, J., Petscher, Y., Fien, H., Stanley, C., Gearin, B., & Gaab, N. (2022). [Dyslexia in the context of social work: Screening and early intervention](#). *Families in Society, 103*(3), 269–280.
- Shahaeian, A., Wang, C., Tucker-Drob, E., Geiger, V., Bus, A. G., & Harrison, L. J. (2018). [Early shared reading, socioeconomic status, and children’s cognitive and school competencies: Six years of longitudinal evidence](#). *Scientific Studies of Reading: The Official Journal of the Society for the Scientific Study of Reading, 22*(6), 485–502.
- Sharma, N., Masood, J., Singh, S. N., Ahmad, N., Mishra, P., Singh, S., & Bhattacharya, S. (2019). [Assessment of risk factors for developmental delays among children in a rural community of North India: A cross-sectional study](#). *Journal of Education and Health Promotion, 8*, 112.
- Sirin, S. R. (2005). [Socioeconomic status and academic achievement: A meta-analytic review of research](#). *Review of Educational Research, 75*(3), 417–453.
- Sperry, D. E., Sperry, L. L., & Miller, P. J. (2019). [Reexamining the verbal environments of children from different socioeconomic backgrounds](#). *Child Development, 90*(4), 1303–1318.
- Sudry, T., Zimmerman, D. R., Yardeni, H., Joseph, A., Baruch, R., Grotto, I., Greenberg, D., Eilenberg, R., Amit, G., Akiva, P., Tsadok, M. A., Rize, Y., Zaworbach, H., Uziel, M., Ben Moshe, D., Lior Sadaka, I., Bachmat, E., Freedman, J., & Sadaka, Y. (2022). [Standardization of a developmental milestone scale using data from children in Israel](#). *JAMA Network Open, 5*(3), e222184.
- Tacke, N. F., Bailey, L. S., & Clearfield, M. W. (2015). [Socio-economic status \(SES\) affects infants’ selective exploration](#). *Infant and Child Development, 24*(6), 571–586.
- Taylor, N., Donovan, W., Miles, S., & Leavitt, L. (2009). [Maternal control strategies, maternal language usage and children’s language usage at two years](#). *Journal of Child Language, 36*(2), 381–404.

- Thomas, P., Zahorodny, W., Peng, B., Kim, S., Jani, N., Halperin, W., & Brimacombe, M. (2012). [The association of autism diagnosis with socioeconomic status](#). *Autism*, *16*(2), 201–213.
- Tourangeau, K., Le, T., & Nord, C. (2005). *Early Childhood Longitudinal Study, kindergarten class of 1998-99 (ECLS-K): Fifth-grade methodology report (NCES 2006-037)*. National Center for Education Statistics, U.S. Department of Education.
- Tran, H.-T., Tseng, Y.-T., Chen, S., Wu, S. K., & Li, Y.-C. (2023). [Moderation of parental socioeconomic status on the relationship between birth health and developmental coordination disorder at early years](#). *Frontiers in Pediatrics*, *11*, 1020428.
- Trentacosta, C. J., Hyde, L. W., Shaw, D. S., Dishion, T. J., Gardner, F., & Wilson, M. (2008). [The relations among cumulative risk, parenting, and behavior problems during early childhood](#). *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, *49*(11), 1211–1219.
- Troller-Renfree, S. V., Hart, E. R., Sperber, J. F., Fox, N. A., & Noble, K. G. (2022). [Associations among stress and language and socioemotional development in a low-income sample](#). *Development and Psychopathology*, 1–9.
- Valentini, N. C., Nobre, G. C., & Duarte, M. G. (2022). [Gross motor skills trajectory variation between WEIRD and LMIC countries: A cross-cultural study](#). *PLOS ONE*, *17*(5), e0267665.
- Vandenbroeck, M. (2020). [Early childhood care and education policies that make a difference](#). In R. Nieuwenhuis & W. Van Lancker (Eds.), *The Palgrave handbook of family policy* (pp. 169–191). Springer International Publishing.
- Vásquez-Echeverría, A., Tomás, C., González, M., Rodríguez, J. I., Alvarez-Nuñez, L., Liz, M., Pérez, M., Rudnitzky, F., Berón, C., Gariboto, G., & Lopez Boo, F. (2022). [Developmental disparities based on socioeconomic status and sex: An analysis of two large, population-based early childhood development assessments in Uruguay](#). *Early Child Development and Care*, *192*(12), 1857–1875.
- Walker, D., Greenwood, C., Hart, B., & Carta, J. (1994). [Prediction of school outcomes based on early language production and socioeconomic factors](#). *Child Development*, *65*(2), 606–621.
- Walker, S. P., Wachs, T. D., Grantham-McGregor, S., Black, M. M., Nelson, C. A., Huffman, S. L., Baker-Henningham, H., Chang, S. M., Hamadani, J. D., Lozoff, B., Gardner, J. M. M., Powell, C. A., Rahman, A., & Richter, L. (2011). [Inequality in early childhood: Risk and protective factors for early child development](#). *The Lancet*, *378*(9799), 1325–1338.

- Wei, Q. W., Zhang, J. X., Scherpbier, R. W., Zhao, C. X., Luo, S. S., Wang, X. L., & Guo, S. F. (2015). High prevalence of developmental delay among children under three years of age in poverty-stricken areas of China. *Public Health, 129*(12), 1610–1617.
- Wolf, S., Reyes, R. S., Weiss, E. M., & McDermott, P. A. (2021). Trajectories of social-emotional development across pre-primary and early primary school. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology, 75*, 101297.
- Yates, T., Cheatham, G. A., Fetting, A., Shaffer, L., & Santos, R. M. (2008). *Research synthesis on screening and assessing social-emotional competence*. The Center on the Social and Emotional Foundations for Early Learning.
- Ye, A., Yan, S., Huang, K., Mao, L., Ge, X., Weng, T., Zuo, A., Tao, X., & Tao, F. (2019). Maternal intelligence quotient and motor development in early childhood: The mediating role of mother's education. *Journal of Paediatrics and Child Health, 55*(1), 87–94.
- Zivan, M., & Horowitz-Kraus, T. (2020). Parent-child joint reading is related to an increased fixation time on print during storytelling among preschool children. *Brain and Cognition, 143*, 105596.
- Zwicker, J. G., Missiuna, C., Harris, S. R., & Boyd, L. A. (2012). Developmental coordination disorder: A review and update. *European Journal of Paediatric Neurology, 16*(6), 573–581.